

On the Study of the Uptake of Calcium Tracer by Strontium Oxalate.

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In the present investigation analogy amongst the oxalates of strontium and calcium has been mainly the subject matter of study. Fluorides have also been included with a comparative outlook. Distribution study with different forms of calcium and strontium oxalates as hosts and Ca^{45} and $\text{Sr}^{90,90}$ as guests has been thoroughly investigated.

It has been found that just like $\text{SrCaO}_4 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcium has got a corresponding compound. Calcium oxalate monohydrate is mixed crystal-forming with corresponding hydrate of strontium.

Trace amount of strontium can be removed from the system by carrying with calcium fluoride in presence of excess of fluoride.

A search of the literature¹ shows that there are three hydrates of calcium oxalate. The monohydrate is the stable variety, the dihydrate preponderates when calcium oxalate is precipitated in acid medium and the trihydrate is the prominent phase when the oxalate in question is precipitated from ammoniacal solution. The later two hydrates are however unstable and are ultimately converted into the monohydrate on prolonged standing. Only brief mention has been made about the two hydrates of strontium oxalate with 2.5 and 1 molecule of water.

Coprecipitation study under experimental condition for the three hydrates of calcium with strontium as major component and Ca^{45} as tracer has been undertaken. This may give us evidence regarding the existence of hydrates of strontium oxalate. Information about the morphological relationship between these compounds of calcium and strontium can also be derived from this study.

Side by side, the uptake of strontium tracer with calcium oxalate under different experimental conditions has also been studied. Uptake of strontium tracer by calcium fluoride has also been included in our study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ca^{45} with high specific activity and $\text{Sr}^{90} + \text{Sr}^{90}$ were supplied by Aes, Trombay. All the chemicals, such as strontium chloride, calcium chloride, acetic acid etc, used in this investigation, were of analar quality. Description of a typical experiment will clarify the procedure adopted. A solution of strontium chloride was taken in a beaker. Mineral acid was neutralised with ammonia. It was made 3N with acetic acid. Ammonium oxalate

1. Kohlchutter and Marti, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1930, 13A, 929.

from a burette was added dropwise to the solution and the medium was kept on constant stirring. A known volume of solution was pipetted out by a device with a filter paper cap at the tip. The amount of Ca^{45} left in the solution was estimated from the known volume by isotopic dilution procedure² adding known amount of calcium. The amount of strontium left in the solution was estimated by evaporating a portion of the solution with sulphuric acid and weighing as SrSO_4 .

A short description of procedure for removal of strontium for subsequent determination of calcium by isotopic dilution should be briefly mentioned. To a known amount of clear solution after separation from strontium oxalate, a known amount of calcium chloride solution was added. Both strontium and calcium were precipitated as carbonate. The carbonate was dissolved in nitric acid and evaporated to dryness and heated at 140° for 24 hr. The calcium was extracted by washing with acetone. The acetone was driven out and calcium was precipitated as oxalate and after several washing by centrifugation it was slurried with acetone and was transferred into the counting tray with a medicine dropper. Calcium oxalate was dried and counted with an end-window Geiger-Muller counter having window thickness of 3.5 mg/cm^2 . Activity was corrected for self absorption and the results were computed accordingly.

In case of measuring strontium activity (Sr^{89} and Sr^{90}) Y^{90} which grows from Sr^{90} was separated by adding natural yttrium and precipitating yttrium as hydroxide. It was washed and dissolved in hydrochloric acid. Yttrium hydroxide was again precipitated in presence of calcium chloride. The solutions from the hydroxide precipitate were mixed together, made up to volume and strontium activity was measured with a liquid counter. The yttrium hydroxide precipitate was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and absence of strontium activity was confirmed by determination of the half-life of Y^{90} .

In the study of coprecipitation of Sr tracer by calcium fluoride, the following procedure was adopted. The strontium activity was added to a solution of calcium chloride. Solution was made just ammoniacal. Different fractions of calcium fluoride were precipitated by adding different quantities of sodium fluoride. The extent of precipitation of CaF_2 was computed from the knowledge of sodium fluoride added. The solution left after precipitation was acidified and any yttrium activity left in the solution was removed in the way already described.

D and λ were calculated from the following expressions:--

$$D = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solid}}}{\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{soln.}}}; \quad \lambda = \frac{\log \left[\frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}} \right]}{\log \left[\frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}} \right]}$$

Results are given in tables-I-III.

TABLE I

On the study of the uptake of Ca^{45} by strontium oxalate under different experimental conditions.

Nature of host.	%Sr. ppted.	%Uptake Ca^{45} .	D	λ	Average
(a) In 3N acetic acid medium stirred for five minutes.					
Temp. : 30°					
$\text{SrC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	27.0	48.5		2.1	2.1
	34.1	60.3		2.2	
	50.6	74.1		1.9	
	63.2	89.8		2.2	
(b) Medium-3N acetic acid shaken for 5 days.					
Temp. : 35°					
$\text{SrC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.7	44.0	3.4		3.3
	29.6	56.5	3.1		
	40.7	69.9	3.4		
(c) In ammoniacal medium stirred for 5 minutes.					
Temp. : 30°					
	11.3	23.6		2.5	
	12.4	26.9		2.4	
	16.2	58.6		5.0	
	22.8	49.9		2.7	
	23.0	64.5		4.0	
	46.3	54.6		1.3	
(d) With externally formed host medium 3N acetic acid.					
Temp. : 35°					
$\text{SrC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	32.9	20.1	.51		.52
	54.7	37.7	.51		
	65.5	50.6	.54		

TABLE II

On the study of the uptake of strontium tracer by different forms of calcium oxalate.

Nature of host.	%Ca ppted.	%Uptake of Sr.	λ	D	Average
(a) In 3N acetic acid medium stirred for five minutes.					
Temp. : 30°					
$\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	12.6	10.4	.80		
	38.1	26.1	.63		
	61.7	38.2	.50		
	78.2	50.6	.46		
(b) In 3N acetic acid medium. Shaken for 4 days					
Temp. : 35°					
$\text{SrC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	34.1	9.3	.23	.20	
	55.0	16.6	.23	.16	
	80.2	29.5	.22	.10	
(c) In ammoniacal medium. Stirred for five minutes.					
Temp. : 35°					
$\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	24.2	22.9	.94		
	38.2	32.8	.82		
	56.4	43.9	.70		
	73.7	58.0	.65		
(d) With externally formed host ($\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$). In 3N acetic acid medium					
Temp. : 35°					
Time in days.	%Ca ppted.	%Uptake of Sr.			
1	54.8	1.8			
2	54.8	3.5			
4	54.8	0.9			
7	54.8	0.1			

TABLE III

On the study of the uptake of strontium tracer by calcium fluoride.

% Ca pptd.	% Uptake of Sr.	λ	D	Average
(a) Stirred for 5 minutes. Temperature: 31.5°C.				
39.5	17.9	.39		.38
52.5	25.8	.40		
65.8	43.6	.38		
79.0	40.9	.34		
(b) Shaken for 5 days. Temperature: 35°C				
43.4	27.9	.57	.50	
72.3	43.4	.44	.29	
86.7	51.1	.36	.16	

DISCUSSION

In table I are given the partition values of strontium oxalate as host under different experimental conditions and Ca^{45} as guest. The results show that in acetic acid medium the guest component is taken up through mixed crystal formation. This has been verified both by instantaneous precipitation (in examination of λ values) and by equilibrating the mother liquor in presence of internally formed host component for five days (in verification of D values). Both the heterogeneous and homogeneous distribution factors are found to be constant. It will not be out of place to mention that the solid phase after the period of equilibration was found to contain 2.5 molecules of water. Constancy of both D and λ gives a strong evidence that probably calcium oxalate has not a hydrate like that of strontium.

The monohydrate of strontium oxalate was prepared by precipitating strontium oxalate in acetic acid medium and washing it with water and finally with alcohol and keeping it at about 50°C for a long time till constant weight. It was powdered and filtered through 120 mesh. Minimum time of attainment of equilibrium was determined as is usually done. It was found that equilibrium is attained in about 4 days. For the verification of D [vide table I (c)], we, therefore, equilibrated the solid for five days in a saturated solution of the host containing calcium tracer. A glance at table I (c) will show that distribution factor D is almost constant. The monohydrate of strontium oxalate, therefore, takes up calcium through mixed crystal formation thereby showing morphological analogy existing among these compounds.

No sign of mixed crystal formation is shown when strontium oxalate containing calcium tracer is precipitated in ammoniacal medium.

From this study it becomes evident that the monohydrate of strontium oxalate is morphologically analogous to that of calcium. It becomes further evident that calcium also forms a hydrate with 2.5 moles of water like strontium. Question naturally arises whether the dihydrate of calcium oxalate as mentioned in the earlier literature² is nothing but the 2.5 hydrate. That question can be verified if strontium tracer is coprecipitated with calcium oxalate in acetic acid medium.

A glance at table-II(a), which gives the results of coprecipitation made under condition, favourable for the formation of calcium oxalate dihydrate, will show that strontium tracer is not taken up through mixed crystal formation. So the first phase that separates in case of calcium oxalate precipitation is neither the 2.5 hydrate nor the monohydrate. Probably, the claim that it is a dihydrate of calcium oxalate is correct.

It is of interest to point out that on equilibrating the internally formed system [vide Table-II(b)] for three days, λ becomes constant but D is not. This is probably due to the extremely slow rate of recrystallisation and diffusion. However, it can be concluded that calcium oxalate monohydrate takes up strontium tracer through mixed crystal formation. That the rate is extremely slow has been verified by equilibrating externally formed monohydrate, powdered and filtered through 120 mesh, in presence of strontium tracer in calcium chloride solution. The uptake is negligibly small.

In ammoniacal solution the uptake of strontium by calcium oxalate follows an adsorption pattern which indicates that probably the trihydrate analogue of calcium in case of strontium does not exist.

Table III shows the uptake of strontium tracer by calcium fluoride. It is evident that freshly formed calcium fluoride takes up strontium tracer through mixed crystal formation. On equilibrating the internally formed fluoride for five days, it is found that neither λ nor D is constant, which suggests that freshly formed calcium fluoride differs in morphology from the aged samples, as has been noticed in several cases in this laboratory³. But it is of interest to comment that though the partition factor in case of CaF_2 , as host and strontium tracer as guest is less than unity, yet it has been observed that in presence of excess of fluoride ion all the strontium tracer is taken up if all the calcium is precipitated as fluoride.

It is to be noted that from a simple coprecipitation study we have been able to observe the following:

- (a) Calcium oxalate has probably got the 2.5 hydrate like that of strontium oxalate;
- (b) Monohydrate of calcium oxalate is mixed-crystal forming with the corresponding compound of strontium;
- (c) Probably strontium oxalate does not form any di- or trihydrate like calcium.

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